

Innovation Skills in Engineering Education as a Catalyst for Sustainability: a preliminary Literature Review

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Abstract

The research unfolds a preliminary literature review to establish the state of the art regarding sustainability and its relationship with developing innovative skills in engineering. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was the method employed through a structured approach for designing, conducting, and reporting with systematic stages, taking like the primary goal the bias reduction and increasing the reproducibility of the results to ensure the transparency in the process, enhancing the credibility and reliability of the findings. The review assessed the current knowledge production of innovative skills in engineering students and how they impact sustainable development. It aims to thoroughly examine related works by analyzing their contributions and identifying areas that warrant further investigation. The resulting narrative allowed for a comprehensive overview of the relation, identifying gaps in existing knowledge and potential avenues for methodological enhancement. The results show that most of the contributions are devoted to interventions in which curricular approaches intend to create new learning scenarios for students, and therefore, students are the center of action. Still, few works stress the teaching practice or the other resources management, showing a set of interesting gaps, especially considering that exemplarity and inspiration are variables explored to foster the higher education process in engineering in different approaches.

Keywords: Innovation; Engineering Education; sustainability; Higher education.

1 Introduction

Sustainability is a multidimensional concept that promotes ensuring the well-being of current and future generations through the responsible management of resources, equitable development, and long-term resilience. For this reason, sustainability is based on four pillars: environmental, social, political, and economic. Therefore, the environment can be seen as a system, where a community lives and interacts in harmony and respect, going beyond the ecological aspect; the social aspect is part of the environmental resources focusing on the well-being of individuals and communities, the political aspect is related to the policy framework to manage the resources, and the economic aspects relate to fostering economic growth considering equity and respect (UNESCO, 2023).

This vision is established in the Global Sustainable Management Strategy 2020-2030, which started in 2019 with the strategy's baseline for operation, then transformed into policy in 2020, which was structured through the road map to be adopted in 2021 and declared as Phase II. Later, in 2022, staff training began addressing the Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) certification, and in 2023, UNESCO introduced the Environmental and Social Safeguards Framework (ESSF) (UNESCO, 2023). Currently, this vision continues to evolve according to global conditions, highlighting the role of education in raising citizens' awareness to promote critical thinking guided by the principles of equity, collaboration, and inclusion (UNESCO, 2017).

Many countries have adopted The Global Sustainable Management strategy, including Colombia, and institutions like the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OCDE) support member and partner countries in integrating sustainability into their policies and practices through policy advice, policy

coherence, capacity building, monitoring, review of strategies, and adoption alternatives and learning. This support is addressed in four action areas: i) ways and tools to apply the sustainable development Goals (SDG), ii) data analysis for monitoring the implementation, iii) support for integrating planning and experiences, and finally, iv) reflection and improvement (OCDE, 2017).

In this context, the OCDE has developed a structure addressed by the Oslo Manual, which has been adapted according to the conditions of different territories like Bogota Manual oriented mainly to developing countries or Frascati Manual for developed countries (OECD & Eurostat, 2018). This structure is supported by external tools like the Global Innovation Index (GII), which is monitored by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). This measure observes the innovation dynamic from incomes, resources, capacities, results and impacts; which are, in turn, transversal to the four sustainable pillars: environmental, social, political and economic. Thus, one of the most important topics related to educational issues, at all levels, are: knowledge absorption, knowledge production and knowledge transfer (GII, 2019).

Colombia has prioritized science development through diverse strategies; one of those is the Council of the Wise, a group of experts in different areas charged by the government of Colombia to produce recommendations about the country's future, including sustainable development. The recommendations of the International Council of the Wise, known in Spanish as *Misión de Sabios*, outline specific goals for balanced development, including quality education and productive growth. The National Policy for Science, Technology, and Innovation, outlined in CONPES 4069 (In Colombia, the Consejo Nacional de Política Económica y Social CONPES is a set of policies oriented to attend specific problems relate to social and economic aspects), sets a 10-year roadmap emphasizing sustainable development. However, challenges persist, such as insufficient STEAM vocations and weak knowledge transfer environments. The Missions oriented Policies – those that emerge for government strategies called Missions, for example, *Misión de Sabios* – aims to address these gaps, explicitly focusing on science for peace and citizenship. Moreover, Knowledge absorption and production in Colombia are close to the global statistical average. However, Knowledge transfer is significantly lower; this indicates that the absorption of knowledge to improve sustainability by society and industry is still low (COMPITE, 2021).

At the regional level, for example, in places located in the Andean mountains, such as Boyacá province, which are characterized by its biodiversity, the priorities for sustainable development include discussions about bio-economy that involve topics like the impact on agriculture, water management, and formulation of a new sustainable model. Despite advancements, challenges remain, including brain drain and the need for academia-industry collaboration. Considering that globally, initiatives emphasize experiential learning and innovative teaching methods to bridge knowledge gaps, in the same way, this work aims to strengthen Boyacá's scientific ecosystem by designing educational approaches that use real-world challenges and critical social needs as learning triggers for promoting the innovation skills, and consequently to improve the region's competitiveness by knowledge transfer.

Knowledge transfer implies developing appropriate solutions, and the engineering professions play a relevant role in the process (Newman, 2024). The term 'appropriate' involves many dimensions, including the sustainability view. These solutions will be more significant if engineering faculties are closer to the industrial and social sectors, taking advantage of their interdependent relation (professions/ employment), which appears usual, but what happens with the effectiveness of this link? Then, an extra question emerges ¿how can we enhance creative and innovative skills in engineering education, exploiting the relationship with society and industry to design appropriate solutions from a sustainability view?

In a Colombian employer survey on human capital, respondents indicated increased difficulty recruiting workers, rising from 36% in 2009 to 61% in 2022. This figure is lower than the global statistic average. According to the Chief executive Officer's (CEO), the gap is associated with quality, quantity, and skill pertinence challenges, emphasizing the ability to transform theory into appropriate results; this context contrasts with the number of bachelor's graduates, which increased by 16,7% between 2015 and 2021 (Consejo Privado de Competitividad, 2023).

A similar situation occurs in different territories. According to UNESCO, some global education challenges to promote sustainable development are environmental awareness, curriculum integration, teacher training, interdisciplinary approaches, global citizenship, partnership and collaboration, access to education, innovation and technology, lifelong learning, monitoring, and evaluation (UNESCO, 2020). Likewise, it is also important to consider alternatives for facing these challenges through new educational interventions that involve, for example, the design of Active Learning (AL) strategies or student-centered approaches. The AL involves interpreting phenomena through various lenses to understand the world, where learners assimilate the knowledge simultaneously whereas they live an experience (Binguier et al., 1980); in turn, this process needs to have a meaningful impact on the learner and their community or institution, demonstrating its utility value. Thus, the abilities of reflection, abstraction, and concretion play a relevant role in successful learning through experiences (Kolb, 2014).

The student-centered approaches are usually designed to promote critical thinking and collaborative work among diverse knowledge areas. It provides strategies to encourage students to explore new ideas and perspectives, resulting in improved performance among engineering students, particularly in STEAM and, consequently, in an alternative for promoting creativity and innovation skills (Freeman et al., 2014).

2 Method

This work is an exploratory literature review to assess the current knowledge of innovative skills among engineering students and how they impact sustainable development. It aims to thoroughly examine related works by analyzing their contributions and identifying areas that warrant further investigation (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). The research question guiding the overall study evaluates each study's contribution. The resulting narrative serves as a comprehensive overview of the topic, identifying gaps in existing knowledge and potential avenues for methodological enhancement (Boland et al., 2017).

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was the method employed. PRISMA offers a structured approach for designing, conducting, and reporting systematic reviews, with the primary goal of reducing bias and increasing the reproducibility of the results (Moher et al., 2009). Following PRISMA guidelines ensures that the review process is transparent and methodologically sound, enhancing the credibility and reliability of the findings.

To identify relevant information, the search focused on three main clusters: active learning, higher education and sustainability. The search was conducted in the Scopus data base using the following equation:

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(TITLE-ABS-KEY(("transform* learn*" OR "activ* lean*" OR "student focused lean*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(("higher education" OR "higher education institution*" OR "hei*" OR "universit*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY "sustainable development" OR "SDG" OR "2030 agenda"))
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Initially, 111 documents were retrieved. These were filtered using exclusion criteria such as publication date, document type, type of results, and relation with the topic. The final dataset consisted of 70 documents, as shown in Figure 1. We include the date rank from 2015 to 2024, coinciding with the implementation of the 2023 agenda. In the reviewing process, we also consider the type of documents and the quality of the publication. Therefore, we only selected articles and book chapters.

Regarding the content of the papers, we applied two filters; the first filter was related to the stage of the research process, choosing only final publications that provide more details, in-depth analysis, and thorough discussions. The second filter was the topic coherence with the research question. This last was the only one applied with a manual review through a careful evaluation, ensuring a precise selection of relevant papers.

Figure 1. PRISMA chart (Source: the authors, 2024).

We used a bibliometric tool, such as a visual strategy, to analyze documents and identify relationship variables and information trends. This analysis allowed for linking insights contexts with the expected research outputs.

3 Results and discussion

Taking into account the limit established with the keyword used in the research question presented in the method: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("transform* learn*" OR "activ* lean*" OR "student focused lean*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (("higher education" OR "higher education institution*" OR "hei*" OR "universit*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY "sustainable development" OR "SDG" OR "2030 agenda). The trends appreciated in knowledge production increased during the pandemic and post-pandemic period, as depicted in Figure 2. This rise was due to the global situation bumping out the socio-economic challenges. However, by 2022, the trend declined as life returned to normal. Most countries interested in the topic are European, with only Brazil and Australia from outside Europe in the top ten. The results show that the European Union is more committed to the explored topics.

Note: Left figure, production by year. Right figure, the production by country.

Figure 2. Knowledge production (Source: Scopus 2024)

The knowledge is associated in more than 50% by two sub-areas, social and environmental sciences, followed by energy and engineering with 25%. In contrast, health, art, and agriculture are the sub-areas with lower production, as depicted in Figure 3. This landscape shows an opportunity for deeper exploration in the engineering sub-area. Another essential characteristic is that 80% of publications that are part of the knowledge body are articles; this means that the studied sample represents contributions that have faced a strict evaluation process.

Note: Left figure, sub-area classification. Right figure, document type.

Figure 3. Documents classification (Source: Scopus 2024)

About the content of the 70 documents, the trend has evolved from emphasizing critical thinking and transformative learning to complementing sustainable development, as depicted in Figure 4. These concepts are encompassed in a process that begins with an information analysis from diverse perspectives. Likewise, the results show that students are encouraged to reflect and propose solutions, contributing to sustainable development, but there are few details about how to do that.

Figure 4. research trend (Source: The authors 2024, though VOSviewer)

The research results have focused on the node sustainable development, with two clusters of information: transformative learning and teaching, as shown in Figure 5. In transformative learning, the most recently explored topics are related to engineering education, specifically curriculum, and students. Regarding the teaching cluster, the more recent issues developed are innovation, teaching training, and educational development.

Figure 5. co-occurrence key word analysis (Source: The authors 2024, through VOSviewer)

Two clusters relate to well-founded frameworks about transformative learning. Mezirow defines transformative learning as a continuous process involving understanding, structuring, reflection, depth, and purpose; this proposal is based on thought, feeling, and acting. This process has two layers: the first is the curriculum, which encompasses a set of courses, learning experiences, and educational activities designed for a degree; the second is learning support, which is associated with the experience that serves as a critical thinking trigger to transform individual and social perspectives, values, vision, and discourse (Mezirow, 2000); as well as sustainable development.

One route to connect layers is teaching, like the approach that encourages students to take an active role in their learning, working in teams to solve complex, open-ended problems (Jatmiko et al., 2018). Thus, current trends open the door to exploring educational development approaches toward sustainability through topics like teaching training and educative innovation.

Despite of the large number of publications, the SDG's indicator of the advance in achieving goals shows the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 "Quality Education" in a worrisome scenario, as depicted in Figure 6. The go-ahead tendency is correct, but the advance is too slow to achieve the goal: "to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all " (CEPAL, 2024).

Figure 6. SDG's trend indicators (Source: CEPAL 2024, The Challenge of Accelerating the 2030 Agenda in Latin America and the Caribbean: Transitions towards Sustainability)

The review analysis results show that researchers focus on transformative learning to support sustainable development. However, to solve the question "How? And when?" it is necessary to explore educational frameworks and their elements like content, approaches, management, and evaluation, as well as their actors or participants, teachers, students, and stakeholders.

4 Concluding remarks

This work provides a framework to address deep research, using a strong background of approaches to enhance innovation skills for sustainability inspired by student-based centered models. Thus, observing the objective of many documents, transformative learning studies have been focused on curricula and students; however, the latest trends are oriented to a born trend on teaching training and education, offering a wide view of perspectives for future research.

This work presents an initial literature review analysis about enhancing innovation skills in engineering education, taking transformative teaching as an option. This work provides a preliminary framework for researching the topic and understanding how student-centered learning approaches foster innovative skills and how transformative teaching is a challenge for truly transformative learning. Although observing the consulted works' purposes, transformative learning studies have focused on curricula and students, but, the latest trends show teaching training and innovation for education as alternatives for offering a comprehensive view of perspectives for future research.

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